

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA)

Identifying Tiger Stripes with
Machine Learning

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1 Executive summary

The Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA) possesses a collection of over 158 distinct tiger skins obtained through encounters with illegal wildlife traders in physical and online markets. Each tiger's stripes are as unique as fingerprints, and the ultimate goal is to establish a globally accessible method and database that enables law enforcement agencies and researchers to identify individual tigers based on their stripe patterns. Every skin is associated with one or more traders, and the database also includes confiscated tiger skins and carcasses. Periodically, new skins are added to the database and carefully compared to determine if they are duplicate images or represent the same skin captured from different angles, which can provide valuable insights for law enforcement. The challenge at hand is to create a user-friendly tool for recognizing individual tigers based on their stripe patterns and utilizing this information to enhance enforcement efforts and combat the illegal trade of tiger skins, carcasses, and live animals.

2 Background

2.1 Previous Approaches

There have only been a handful of approaches proposed related to tiger identification. In [23], a method based on convolutional neural networks is proposed to identify individual tigers. The experimental data is obtained from 40 Amur tigers in Tieling Guaipo Tiger Park, China. The proposed system, deployed and used in India, uses a program called "extract compare" to identify live tigers [18]. The software fits a 3D surface model to the tiger image to capture a pattern that is not affected by the camera angle or the tiger's posture. It then compares the new pattern with previous patterns stored in a library and displays the most likely matches (an example can be seen in Fig. 1). Images suitable for this process may come from researchers, tourists or camera traps. The resulting database of match results can be used for monitoring population size and other parameters, determining the fate of individual animals, encouraging cooperation between different research groups and more.

Figure 1: (a) The tiger photo is uploaded and the outline of the green mesh is manually added by the user. (b) Extract and compare automatically flattens the pattern inside the green mesh and converts it to a binary image. This is then compared to other tiger stripes.

Although it works well, it requires many manual steps in the process of re-identification. Once an image is uploaded, an outline of the tiger's main body must be made manually before it is flattened and the stripes are extracted for comparison.

2.2 ATRW: A Benchmark for Amur Tiger Re-identification in the Wild

The paper related to Amur Tiger Re-identification in the Wild benchmark (ATRW) introduces a novel large-scale dataset for Amur tiger re-identification in the wild, which is an important task for wildlife conservation [15]. Amur Tigers are classified as an endangered species, with a remaining population of fewer than 600. Computer vision techniques are used for re-identification, in order to obtain accurate population counts and track wildlife trajectory. One major hurdle outlined in the paper is the fact that wildlife data have a wider range of poses, complex natural backgrounds, and unconstrained lighting conditions, as opposed to datasets used for pedestrian and car re-identification [15]. There is also a lack of data and benchmarks, showing the need for an automated, systematic wildlife re-identification system.

The presented dataset contains over 8,000 video clips from 92 Amur tigers, with bounding box, pose keypoint, and tiger identity annotations.

Figure 2: Framework of Amur tiger re-ID system. Motion sensor triggers detector on smart camera to obtain tiger images. Tiger images are fetched and pose estimation and re-ID algorithm are run to produce tiger-to-camera association and determine moving trajectory.

The proposed method (as seen in Fig. 2) uses precise pose parts modeling in deep neural networks to handle large pose variations of tigers. First, a bounding box and the view orientation of the image are annotated. Then, professionals determine the tiger’s identity based on temporal and appearance cues. Furthermore, as the tiger movement causes large pose variations, skeleton keypoints are annotated, which are used to align and normalize the tiger, and provide precise modeling of the tiger to improve the accuracy of re-ID algorithms.

The paper evaluates the proposed method and several baseline algorithms on the dataset and shows that the proposed method achieves notable performance improvement over existing re-ID methods.

3 Data Overview

3.1 Dataset description

The EIA provided a mixture of EIA-specific and ATRW images (N = 6218 files, 6141 unique filenames, in jpeg format) of ‘live’ tigers, tiger carcasses and tiger skins. The images are collected from a range of sources (camera traps, photographers and investigators). The ATRW data is publicly available at: <https://cvwc2019.github.io/challenge.html>

Figure 3: The number of times different tiger IDs appear in the dataset.

A tiger may have more than one ID [15]. Separate IDs are assigned to the left and right sides of a tiger.

The file name is comprised of an image number, temporary ID (optional) and category (optional).

Paired with the data are 3 files:

- A csv file containing the file names, temporary tiger IDs and annotations of the view angle.
- A JSON file containing the file names and key points for the training set (N = 1887).
- A JSON file containing the file names and key points for the testing set (N = 1764).

Category	Number of Images
Unlabelled	4821
Skin	696
Live	338
Carcass	198
ADS	87
nan	78
Blank	32

Table 1: Distribution of classes

3.2 Data Limitations

There is a vast range of sizes and resolutions of tiger images. There are also not many images per unique tiger with the mean number being 6, and a maximum of 125. Although the majority of tigers have multiple images, these images are from a single angle.

3.2.1 Data Variation

As expected, there are differences between the images of live tigers and the skins and carcasses. Such difference includes multiple viewing angles, carcass positions, the position of the live tigers in the image, etc. which make identification a more challenging task.

3.2.2 Ground Truth Uncertainty and Related Issues

There are 964 unique tiger IDs for the images of live tigers in the dataset, but there is no system in place during image capture to ascertain whether two images believed to belong to different tigers actually do belong to different ones. It is not clear if this corresponds to the same number of live tigers, given that a single tiger could be assigned multiple IDs. We believe this is likely, given estimations of there being around 600 Amur tigers left in the wild [15]. This issue poses a major challenge for both model training and validation.

In addition, none of the skins has an identified live tiger counterpart in the dataset, meaning technically they all have temporary IDs.

Some useful information regarding the dataset:

- Combination of live tigers, tiger carcasses, and tiger skins.
- Different lighting in different images.
- Multiple tigers in one image sometimes.
- A .csv file that contains all the image IDs. Each ID also has a reference on it that indicates if it's been recognized as being in another photo too. Links between photos have been made only between live tigers and other live tigers.
- Data preparation/organization is needed, given the images are not machine learning ready
- The .jpg IDs are split into 6 types: 'Skin', 'Live', 'Carcass', 'ADS', and 'nan'. There are 3 columns in the .csv file: 'file' contains the file name in the form of 'Skin/Live/Carcass... .jpg'; 'ID' contains the temporary or true ID; 'angle' contains the angle of the photo if known.
- Ground Dino and SAM model might need to be tested on the full dataset and see how it works.

4 Database

4.1 Centralised Data Storage and Process Recording

Centralised data storage and process recording have been considered as a future must-have element of the project. DSG has reviewed Cloud Storage and Cloud Hosting solutions. Taking into account that the EIA is a non-profit organisation, leading cloud solution providers offer special packages.

The recommendation from the team would be to use a data lake for storing raw images and a database for metadata of the files and results of the pipeline steps.

Database Selection Postgres DB or MongoDB have been recommended for the project. The images cannot be stored in the DB in the raw form but can be stored after converting into binary representation. This process may be time-consuming if repeated many times; hence, the recommendation for cloud storage and file reference using name and file path.

The difference between Postgres DB and MongoDB refers to data organization. MongoDB stores data as JSON, which does not require defining the schema. MongoDB allows efficient connection between the front and back end of the application.

Postgres DB allows storing structured and unstructured data (JSON/JSONB) but requires defining the schemas.

Data Loading Data load from pandas to MongoDB can be achieved using PyMongo with the following command:

```
1 db.collection.insert_many(df.to_dict('records'))
```

Data load from pandas to Postgres can be achieved using the following command:

```
1 df.to_sql('table_name', engine)
```

4.2 Suggested Fields for Storing in the Database

1. **file_name**: The name of the tiger picture.
2. **hash of the file**: A unique identifier defined on the file content.
3. Masking process results and metadata.
4. Data Augmentation results and metadata.
5. Applied models results and metadata.
6. Defined tiger ID.

Here's an example Python code snippet for calculating the hash of a file, which provides unique identifiers for each image, using the hashlib library:

```

1 import hashlib
2
3 def calculate_file_hash(file_path):
4     # Create a hash object
5     hasher = hashlib.sha256()
6
7     # Open the file in binary mode
8     with open(file_path, 'b') as f:
9         # Read the file in chunks
10        for chunk in iter(lambda: f.read(4096), b''):
11            # Update the hash object with the current chunk
12            hasher.update(chunk)
13
14    # Get the hexadecimal representation of the hash value
15    file_hash = hasher.hexdigest()
16
17    return file_hash
18
19 # Example usage
20 file_path = 'path_to_your_file'
21 hash_value = calculate_file_hash(file_path)
22 print('File Hash:', hash_value)

```

5 Methods and Results

5.1 Overview

In this project report, we explore two pipelines: A. Vision Transformers with masking 'MAT' Fig. 4 (explained in section 5.2) and B. Sim-CLR-T Fig. 5 (explained in section 5.6). An overview of these two pipelines is presented in Fig. 6

Figure 4: Pipeline A - MAT.

5.2 Pipeline A: Vision Transformer

5.2.1 Masking

The tiger images contain a lot of background data which can basically be treated as noise when comparing the different tiger skins. To optimise the matching, it is favourable to remove the background before performing any similarity searching. We have explored a few different methods to perform this. Firstly, we look to find a bounding box for the tigers in the images. Once we have a bounding box, we segment its contents so we know the exact pixels where the tiger is located.

5.2.2 Grounding DINO

Grounding DINO (Fig. 7) is a state-of-the-art zero-shot, multi-modal image recognition model [16]. The initial class embeddings are created from a list of strings which are embedded in a feature space using a BERT transformer. The images are embedded in a separate feature

Pipeline Sim-CLR-T

Figure 5: Pipeline B - Sim-CLR-T.

space using a SWIN transformer. The cross-modality of the model is enabled by cross-attention layers firstly, during the feature enhancement to produce better-aligned features from the two modalities. In the final decoder, the queries are combined with the image and text features using more cross-attention layers.

5.2.3 YOLO

YOLO (You Only Look Once) [21] is a well-known algorithm that employs a comprehensive neural network to make simultaneous predictions of bounding boxes and class probabilities. It sets itself apart from previous object detection algorithms that relied on adapting classifiers for detection purposes. The popularity of this algorithm stems from its impressive combination of speed and accuracy.

Figure 6: Overall Framework Overview.

Figure 7: Architecture of grounding DINO [16]. Several cross-attention layers are utilised in the feature enhancement and the decoder to allow for the cross-modality of this model.

5.3 Segment anything model (SAM)

Once we have a bounding box, we can use Meta’s SAM [14] to provide a segmentation mask of the tiger. This is another zero-shot algorithm which can take prompts either as pixel coordinates or bounding boxes to produce accurate segmentations of an image, although it cannot classify the segments. Whether it is a live tiger or a tiger skin, it performs well on our dataset, and effectively disregards noise or objects that overlap or completely split the tiger into two. SAM also works by encoding both the prompts and images into separate feature spaces before using a simple mask decoder. The encoders used are not unique, e.g. the image encoder being a pretrained vision transformer MAE [7]. It is the dataset used for the training which was groundbreaking since it contains 11 million images and more than a billion masks. This huge dataset was collected in three stages: (i) an initial manual stage where annotators are asked to segment all objects in an image, (ii) a second semi-automatic

stage where SAM segments an image and labellers are asked to segment anything that SAM has missed, (iii) a third fully automatic stage where SAM is prompted with a grid of points on the image to produce 100 accurate masks per image.

Figure 8: An example of the output from GroundingDINO combined with SAM.

5.4 Mask R-CNN

Although SAM's performance is impressive, it cannot segment tigers in some noisy images. Hence, we try to use Mask R-CNN [9], which extends Faster R-CNN to solve instance segmentation tasks. It achieves this by adding a branch for predicting an object mask in parallel with the existing branch for bounding box recognition. For example, the following figure depicts the SAM and Mask R-CNN outputs in which Mask R-CNN segments two tigers while SAM cannot because of the image's quality.

5.5 Comparison of YOLO and GroundingDINO

Since we have no ground truth for the bounding boxes and segmentation, we cannot provide a quantitative analysis of the two methods. However, upon inspection of example photos, the combination of GroundingDINO and SAM accurately picks out and segments the tigers at about 90%-95% (Fig. 9).

Figure 9: The outputs of SAM and Mask R-CNN.

5.5.1 Data Augmentation

following upon masking (Fig. 10), the data augmentation is performed to improve the generalisation performance as well as the robustness of the model. In our pipeline, we performed data augmentation using the default method from the PyTorch package ¹.

In the training phase, each image is firstly resized into the shape of 224×224 , then a color jitter is applied on each image to randomly change the brightness, contrast, saturation and hue of that image (Fig. 11). Then a random affine transformation is applied to the image and each image then has a 50% of probability to be horizontally flipped around. In the end, all the training images will be normalised to have zero mean and unit standard deviation to stabilize the training process.

5.5.2 Backbone Model

Vision Transformers: The Vision Transformer (ViT) [5] is a deep learning architecture introduced in 2020 that revolutionized the field of computer vision. Traditionally, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been the dominant architecture for image classification tasks.

¹<https://pytorch.org/vision/stable/transforms.html>

Figure 10: The final output, from the masking, and the input into section 5.5.1 is the following.

Figure 11: (a) The variance of the brightness of the tiger images including the background. (b) The variance of the brightness when the background is not included. (c) The variance of the brightness when the background is all black. (c) is the actual input into the transformer. The black background increases the variance which may be an issue, but removing the background may outweigh the disadvantage of a larger variance, especially since the data will be normalised before input.

However, ViT proposed a new approach by adapting the Transformer architecture [25] originally designed for natural language processing, to handle visual data.

The core idea behind ViT is to leverage the self-attention mechanism in Transformers, which allows the model to attend to different regions of the image and capture both local and global context. By incorporating self-attention, ViT eliminates the need for explicit spatial hierarchy encoded by CNNs and enables the model to learn from the relationships between patches.

5.5.3 Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning

Despite the effectiveness of the ViT, training a Transformer requires a large dataset of labeled images to learn meaningful representations. Therefore, in our case, we adopted the pretrained ViT model and applied fine-tuning using our dataset to classify the tigers.

In this study, we chose to use apply the Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) technique to fine-tune the parameters. PEFT is a technique that aims to improve the efficiency of fine-tuning large pretrained models, while achieving comparable or even better performance. Compared with traditional fine-tuning approaches, PEFT does not require fine-tuning all the parameters but only a subset of the parameters, focusing on the most relevant parts of the model for the specific task. In our case, we only fine-tune 0.77% of the original trainable parameters of the Vision Transformer.

5.5.4 Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the results obtained when the ViT model was run when masking was applied to the images and when it was excluded. The Top-1 accuracy is the accuracy of the model's highest probability prediction matching the expected prediction. Top-5 accuracy is the accuracy of any of the model's 5 highest probability predictions matching the expected prediction, while Top-10 accuracy is the accuracy of the model's 10 highest probability predictions. It is evident that masking the images provides better overall accuracy. The better performance of ViT model using the masked images shows that the background of the tiger images

has some effect on model performance. This confirms that removing the background of the images reduces noise and optimizes model performance.

Type	Top-1 Accuracy	Top-5 Accuracy	Top-10 Accuracy
Masked	28.9	55.1	73.3
Unmasked	23.5	42.8	60.4

Table 2: ViT Model Accuracies

5.6 Pipeline B: SimCLR-T

Overview: Here we explore an alternative pipeline, named “**simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations in tiger**” (**SimCLR-T**). In general, the SimCLR-T pipeline includes three components: (1) data augmentation (section 5.6.2), (2) unsupervised representation learning (section 5.6.3), and (3) supervised learning (section 5.7).

The SimCLR-T pipeline takes an image (no matter what size) as the input and first goes through a few data augmentation pipelines to re-scale and perform other augmentation techniques to populate more images, this can be used for both unsupervised (section 5.6.3) and supervised section 5.7) learning setup. The final output from the data augmentation is a few views (2, in our case) of patches randomly generated from the same image in a given size (32*32, in our case) with more descriptions of the method in section 5.6.2.

After the data augmentation, we first go through the unsupervised learning pipeline, with the purpose of creating a representation of the image in a lower-dimensional vector. Since this step is fully unsupervised, we are able to utilize a larger dataset even when the label is not given. Note this is very important for this task itself as good quality labels are not easy to find and require expert knowledge for the annotation.

Once we have the representation from the unsupervised model, finally, our pipeline takes the representation (or the unsupervised model in the previous step) and attach a linear head with whatever the number of class

as the output. This allows us to fine-tune our model with stronger supervision signals from labelled data while utilising the power of self-supervised learning representations. This equivalently can be considered as a sort of transfer learning technique.

5.6.1 SimCLR

SimCLR is a simple SSL framework for contrastive learning of visual representations from unlabeled data [3], which uses contrastive learning to maximize agreement between 2 augmented versions of the same image. The core components of the SimCLR include the following:

1. Generate two random views from the original image
2. Representation learning based on the InfoNCE loss [19].

In the first step, we create a positive pair (x, x^+) , which contains two correlated images from the same original image, with each dimension down-scaled to 32×32 . The positive pair is created based on data augmentation techniques (section 5.6.2); at the same time, for each batch, we get $2N - 1$ negative pairs where N is the number of batch size.

Figure 12: ResNet Illustration [10]

The next step is about representation learning, to do that, we feed data through a model (in our case, the backbone of the model is a ResNet-50 [10], with an illustration in Fig. 12). An overview of this process is shown in Fig.13, once the data is fed through the model, the model returns an embedding vector \mathbf{h} . Then, a projection head $g(\cdot)$ is applied to the embedding vector \mathbf{h} , which produces a final representation $\mathbf{z} = g(\mathbf{h})$. The

projection head $g(\cdot)$ is usually a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) with 2 dense layers. The contrastive learning loss operates on the latent space mapped by the projection head $g(\cdot)$. We can gain the representations \mathbf{h} from the ResNet to learn new downstream tasks by throwing away the projection head $g(\cdot)$.

Figure 13: SimCLR Framework [24]

The lost function for representation learning uses the InfoNCE loss, as shown in Equ. 1. This loss here is applicable for a given positive pair $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^+)$, where \mathbf{z}_i and \mathbf{z}_j are the representations of the points. $\mathbf{1}_{[k \neq i]}$ here is an indicator function and equal to 1 if $k \neq i$ and τ here is the temperature which controls the shape of the logits value distribution. For this case:

$$l_{i,j} = -\log \frac{e^{\{\text{sim}(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)/\tau\}}}{\sum_{k=1}^{2N} \mathbf{1}_{[k \neq i]} e^{\{\text{sim}(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_k)/\tau\}}} \quad (1)$$

5.6.2 Data Augmentation

Preliminary: We first conducted a statistical analysis on the Plain Re-ID train data. Figure 14 presents histograms of all 3393 images in

Figure 14: Histograms of the width and height of images

Dataset	Instance Number	Width			Height		
		Mean	Median	Std	Mean	Median	Std
Plain Re-id Train data	3393	512.2	436.5	321.1	428.3	378.5	224.8
Plain Re-id Test data	1764	645.5	602.5	329.4	416.1	384.0	212.6

Table 3: Statistic table

terms of image width and height. The histograms indicate that the majority of the images have a width size of around 400 and a height size of approximately 400. For efficient image augmentation, we ideally resize the data to a size of (400, 400). Moreover, we summarize the statistics of mean, median and standard deviation on Plain Re-id train data and Plain Re-id test data respectively, as presented in Table 3. It is important to note that there are two sets of data: 'Anno_ReID_train' and 'Anno_ReID_test,' which both contain keypoint ground truth labels. However, we did not conduct a statistical analysis on these labels since they share the same images as Plain Re-id train and test respectively.

Data augmentation - Resizing: Along with the statistical analysis, we design a data augmentation pipeline to perform image re-scaling and augmentation. This approach helps in generating additional images to expand the training set. We utilise imgaug package [11], which converts a

Figure 15: (a) Original tiger image 1 (b) Original tiger image 2 (c) Resized tiger image 1 (d) Resized tiger image 2

set of input images into a new, much larger set of slightly altered images. The pipeline begins with image resizing, which takes an input image and desired dimensions, with a width of x and a height of y . The output of the image resizing step is a resized image with the dimensions (x, y) . Figures in 15 demonstrate the changes before and after resizing. For instance, the original tiger image 1 (a) is in size of around (600, 1000), after resizing (presented as subfigure (c)), the size is (400, 400).

Data augmentation - Methods: After the image resizing step, three pipelines are implemented for data augmentation. In this step, the resized image is passed into an augmentation function that offers three types of augmentation methods: rotation, Gaussian blur, and random cropping. Each augmentation method requires two arguments for further

Figure 16: (a) Rotated tiger image 1 with angle $(-25,25)$. (b) Rotated tiger image 2 with random angle between $(-25,25)$. (c) Rotated tiger image 1 with random angle between $(-45, 45)$. (d) Rotated tiger image 1 with random angle between $(-45,45)$.

Figure 17: (a) Gaussian blur tiger image 1 with sigma value $(30, 90)$. (b) Gaussian blur tiger image 2 with sigma value $(30, 90)$. (c) Gaussian blur tiger image 1 with sigma value $(0, 30)$. (d) Gaussian blur tiger image 2 with sigma value $(0, 30)$.

operation.

1. Rotation augmentation method is to rotate the image by a random value between the arguments passed in. For instance, Figure 16 demonstrates two groups of images that rotated with degree between -25 to 25 and -45 to 45 respectively.
2. Gaussian blur method requires sigma value within a range that the arguments passed in. For instance, Figure 17 presents two groups of images that got Gaussian blur with random sigma value between $(30, 90)$ and $(0, 30)$ respectively.

Figure 18: (a) Cropped tiger image 1 with percentage between 0 to 40%. (b) Cropped tiger image 2 with percentage between 0 to 40%. (c) Cropped tiger image 1 with percentage between 20% to 60%. (d) Cropped tiger image 2 with percentage between 20% to 60%.

3. The crop method randomly crops images by a certain percentage of their height and width. For instance, the group of figures in Figure 18 (a) and (b) are cropped between percentage of 0 to 40%. On the other hand, figure (c) and (d) are cropped between percentage between 20% to 60%.

To explore augmentation techniques in depth, we explored data augmentation with NumPy library. In the NumPy library, we implemented translations, random noise, distortions techniques and random erasing.

1. Translations are simple shifting of a picture in some direction, which accepts the desired direction to move, the number of pixels for shift and behavior of the patch that is left empty when the image has been shifted.
2. Random noise technique is similar to the Gaussian blur from imagu library, which adds additional randomness in the augmented images by applying Gaussian noise.
3. Distortion technique applies continuous shift of the rows or columns of the image-guided by trigonometric functions (cosine or sinus). The resulting image would be “wavy” in horizontal or vertical directions.
4. Random Erasing randomly selects a rectangle region in an image and erases its pixels with random values. In this process, the images

with various levels of occlusion are generated, which reduces the risk of over-fitting and makes the training model robust to occlusion.

5.6.3 Representation Learning

Background: Self-supervised learning (SSL) is a new machine learning paradigm, which derives pseudo labels to guide learning in a fully unsupervised manner². SSL can be broadly divided into two main categories [17]: contrastive and generative. Generative SSL has been used widely to create large-scale models, such as the GPT family [1, 20], representing the current state-of-the-art of artificial intelligence (AI); on the other hand, contrastive SSL, especially a type of method named contrastive learning, has recently attracted increasing attention due to its simplicity and effectiveness. In this report, since the task aims to identify the identity of a tiger given the stripe, which is a discriminative task³, hence we explore the contrastive SSL here.

Figure 19: Self-supervised Learning compares to other machine learning paradigms from [17].

Contrastive learning is a type of self-supervised learning which aims to learn a good representation z for given data $x \in \mathcal{D}$ in an unsupervised manner. The main idea behind contrastive learning is to learn a shared embedding space such that similar data sample pairs (also called a

²A comparison between SSL and other more traditional machine learning paradigms is illustrated in Fig. 19

³Note that representations learnt with generative SSL can also be used for classification tasks, however, it is usually more favourable for generation tasks.

Figure 20: Contrastive learning illustration from [13].

positive pair) (x, x^+) are close to each other, while dissimilar sample pairs (also called a negative pair) (x, x^-) stay far apart (see a visual example in Fig 20) [4]. This can be done by training a neural network to predict whether two instances are similar or dissimilar.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in contrastive learning, and a number of new methods have been proposed, such as SimCLR [3], SwAV [2], MoCo [8] and BYOL [6]. These methods have shown promising results on a variety of tasks. Hence, in this section, we explore one of these methods, called SimCLR and we explain this technique in detail in the next section.

5.6.4 Results and Discussion

Our initial plan was to compare a few different backbone models in order to demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed method. But due to time constraints, we ended up using a ResNet-50 model with random initialisation.

Unfortunately, we were only able to train the model for 10 epochs. More experiments, more data, and longer training times are advised to improve the performance of such a model in the future. Fig. 21 shows the behaviour of the loss function for both training and validation.

Figure 21: Training and Evaluation Loss with SimCLR - unsupervised.

5.7 Alternative neural augmentation - further exploration

Background Given that our dataset is very unbalanced with a large number of classes and few instances per class, we decided to supplement our model training data with synthetic images. We opted for a generative adversarial network (GAN), comprised of one neural network attempting to generate synthetic data points while another learns to differentiate between synthetic and real samples. GAN models are complex to train and computationally intensive, but can generate highly detailed, realistic synthetic data points.

Unconditional Finetuning StyleGAN3 (Fig. 22) is used in this project [12]. Through the use of Fourier features, filtering, 1x1 convolution kernels and other modifications, this generator is equivariant to translation and rotation. This feature is of importance in our project, given that tiger pose varies greatly within the dataset and the images are unaligned. As GANs are computationally intensive to train and require very large datasets, we decided not to train from scratch. Transfer learning is an effective approach for finetuning an existing pretrained StyleGAN3 model [12].

The ARTW re-ID dataset is used for finetuning. The images have been previously aligned and cropped.

Note: As the resizing function included in this process distorts the image, a future task is to use inpainting to extend the background, while not altering the tiger strip pattern. Simple padding of the image will not suffice, as the background is included in the patches that are inputted to SIM-CLR.

A class-independent GAN is trained to explore the viability of transfer learning in the context given the quality and size of the ARTW dataset. During training the Fréchet inception distance (FID) is used to assess the quality of images created by the generative model. The metric summarizes the distance between the Inception feature vectors (i.e. activation taken from the penultimate pooling layer) for real and generated images in the same domain.

Class-conditional GANs Furthermore, we explored class-conditional GANs, in order to supplement class-specific images. Research groups have reported that class-conditioning GANs cause mode collapse in limited data settings, where unconditional GANs produce satisfactory images. In order to prevent this observed mode-collapse, we implement a method leveraging unconditional learning [22]. This strategy starts with an unconditional GAN and gradually injects conditional information into the generator and the objective function, which results in stable training and higher-quality images.

Analysis: A common analysis technique for two-dimensional images is the spatial power spectrum – the square of the 2D Fourier transform of an image. The slope of this 1D spectrum can be compared to the expected indices in different physical limits.

To analyse the quality of the synthetically generated dataset, average 2D power spectra are generated. A radial profile of the 2D power spectrum gives the 1D power spectrum (Fig. 23). The training images in AFHQwild (512x512 resolution) and our input tiger images from the ARTW database are visualized along with the corresponding spectra of random images generated using the pretrained StyleGAN3-T and our fine-tuned StyleGan3-T model. Each plot represents the average power over the given images, computed as outlined in the paper introducing StyleGan3

Figure 22: Modified training objective and architecture of StyleGAN2 that allows for transitioning from the unconditional to the conditional model during the training [22]. This transitioning approach is applied to StyleGAN3 in this project.

Figure 23: a) AFHQwild 2d power spectrum; and b) ATRW 2d power spectrum

[12]. From each image, we subtract the training dataset mean, after which we divide it by the training dataset standard deviation. Note that these normalizing quantities represent the entire dataset reduced to two scalars, and do not vary by colour channel or pixel coordinate. The image is then multiplied with a separable Kaiser window with $\beta = 8$, and its power spectrum is computed as the absolute values of the FFT raised to the second power. This processing is applied to each color channel separately and the result is averaged over them. These spectra are then averaged over all the images in the dataset. The result is plotted on the decibel scale. Bottom: One-dimensional slices of the power spectra at 0° and 45° angles.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

in this project, we explored the use of machine learning technologies, such as vision transformers, SimCLR, SAM, DINO, etc., along with augmentation techniques, to identify tiger stripes and match them to individual tigers. Considering that tigers are subjected to illegal trading, identifying individual tigers could be important towards dealing with illegal trading. Through the development of various approaches, we found that masking significantly improves performance (20%). In addition, in cases where runtime is important, one might have to consider the tradeoff between computational demands and performance, e.g. SimCLR requires a lot of training time to work satisfactorily. For the sake of this DSG challenge, we avoided running algorithms from scratch due to time constraints and instead tried to focus on exploring various existing solutions.

Our work has a few limitations which include: a) using only pretrained vision transformers; however, considering the amount of data available to use it is unlikely that we could train any models from scratch unless we were to incorporate additional data into the model, b) exploring ResNet-50 as the backbone model for SimCLR; other backbone models could be tested to identify other possibilities as well, and c) limited experiments that hinder drawing concrete conclusions about the proposed system.

Nevertheless, most of the limitations could feed into future work where fine-tuning our models and leveraging masking across all models could

potentially yield better results. In addition, using more data and training for more epochs could help to train models that converge and exhibit better performance. Lastly, another aspect could involve exploring different types of models and employing further preprocessing steps that could enhance the representations learnt and subsequently the performance of the models.

7 Team members

7.1 Participants

Kelvin Simatwo is a first year PhD researcher at Loughborough University. He specializes in researching computationally efficient embedded classification algorithms for augmentative and alternative communication devices. He contributed to the project in data exploration, testing the MAT pipeline without masking applied and presentation slides preparation.

Lara Johnson is a PhD in the School of Informatics at the University of Edinburgh. She contributed to the project by facilitating the group, preparing the MAT and Sim-CLR-T pipelines overview and presentation slides preparation.

Jialin Yu is a research fellow in machine learning at the department of statistical science, University College London. His research interests include statistical machine learning, causality and deep learning. He is a participant in the EIA challenge and contributes to data exploration, design and implementation of the SimCLR-T pipeline, report writing, final slides and presentation, as well as offer technical support on machine learning related problems for the team.

Zijie Huang is a PhD candidate at the University of Exeter. Her research interests include explainable machine learning, ethical decision-making and Digital Twin assisted autonomous driving simulation. She contributed to the project in data augmentation and report writing.

Jayesh Choudhari is a Research Scientist at Cube Global Ltd. His research interests include NLP, machine learning, deep learning, and algorithms. As a participant in the EIA challenge he contributed to exploratory data analysis, exploring data augmentation, design and implementation of the Semi-Supervised SimCLR-T pipeline, preparing

final slides and presenting them, preparing the flowchart of the pipeline, and offered technical support on machine learning related problems to the team.

Hanzhi Wang is a PhD candidate at the Cardiff University. His research focuses on machine learning techniques on medical imaging. As a participant in the EIA project, he explored the performance of YOLO on masking problem and contributed to the report writing.

Khashayar Ghamati is a PhD candidate at Hertfordshire University. His research focuses on Human-Robot teaming. As a participant in the EIA challenge, he employed YOLO and Mask RCNN to detect and segment tigers and then compared their results with GroundingDINO and SAM. He also contributed to the report writing.

Nikola Kolev is a PhD candidate at University College London. His research is in fabrication of nanoelectronics using scanning tunneling microscopy (STM). He is also interested in applying machine learning techniques to the field of STM.

7.2 Principal Investigator

Professor Georgios Leontidis is the Director of the Interdisciplinary Centre for Data and AI and a Professor of Machine Learning at the University of Aberdeen. Georgios is a member of the Scottish AI Alliance leadership group and has done foundational and transformative work in machine learning research and its applications in agri-food and sustainability. His work on AI in Agri-Food has been mentioned and cited in policy documents and reports, such as the 2022 foresight report “Thinking about the Future of Food Safety” published by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, and the 2023 European Parliament report “Artificial intelligence in the agri-food sector: applications, risks, and impacts”. Georgios currently (co-)leads a number of funded projects and networks including ‘Enhancing Agri-Food Transparent Sustainability’ (EPSRC), ‘Machine Learning and Expert-based System for Soft Fruit Yield Forecasting’ (Data Lab and Angus Soft Fruits), ‘Data for Net Zero’ (Net Zero Technology Centre), and the ‘Artificial Intelligence in the Biosciences (AiBio-UK) network’ (BBSRC), and directs a team of thirteen PhD students and five Research Associates.

7.3 Challenge Owners

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